

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE ORIENTATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE INFORMATION SOCIETY: EVENTS OF THE PAST AND PROSPECTS OF THE FUTURE

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Abstract. *The concept "innovations" and the maintenance of innovations of the higher education is analyzed in the article. Communication between innovations in business and in education comes to light. The reasons of difficult process of the course of innovative reforms are formulated. The conclusion is: it is need to weighed approach to the happening changes for system of Uzbek education.*

On the one hand, awareness of the future problems that a future graduate will face contributes to the introduction of new subjects, the creation of new teaching methods, the formulation of new, large-scale tasks in education, the final result of which should be the preparation of a person for effective and productive activities in various socially significant situations. In modern state educational standards, this readiness is designated as competencies, about which endless discussions are conducted, since there is no unambiguous definition of the essence of this category.

Keywords: *education, reforms, innovation, J. Dewey, business, contributes, preparation, training, methods, problems, conclusion, readiness, situations.*

Since the introduction of the Uzbek higher education system to the Bologna process, teachers and administrative staff from education have been paying close attention to innovations and their application. Disputes about this are the most fierce. Conferences, seminars, round tables, meetings of ministries and departments involved in innovative topics are organized; plans, strategic directions and practical recommendations for the implementation of innovative projects are created. The range of discussions is very wide: from complete rejection of any innovations in the field of education to full active immersion in innovative teaching methods, accompanied by calls to forget traditional forms and methods of education in the form of lectures, theoretical seminars and explanations from the teacher.

Although not always an active position corresponds to the very concept of "innovation" and its essential characteristics. This circumstance requires, firstly, an appeal to the origins of the concept of "innovation" and, secondly, the study of the approbation of this phenomenon in the early models of American and Western European education.

If we consider innovations in the sense of actively introducing new, creative teaching methods into the educational process, then, oddly enough, it is worth moving from the field of education to the field of entrepreneurship. It was in entrepreneurial activity that the Austrian theorist J. Schumpeter began to consider innovation as a system of new combinations, new ideas and activities, and the innovator as a creator, a creative person whose motives will give joy to himself and to those who will use the results of his work. Schumpeter noted: "The task of

entrepreneurs is to reform and revolutionize the way of production by introducing inventions, and in a general sense – through the use of new technologies for the production of new goods or former goods, but by a new method, thanks to the discovery of a new source of raw materials or a new market for finished products – up to the reorganization of the former and the creation of a new industry ..." [1. p. 302].

The essence of modern innovation is clearly expressed in Schumpeter's concept: the cult of creative thinking, the search for new methods of production of goods and services that society needs, the replication of new samples, etc. elements to meet the growing needs of the population. In the conditions of the information society, the innovative orientation captures not only the field of entrepreneurship, but the very "spirit" of entrepreneurial innovation activity becomes an obligatory element of the work of all social institutions, including educational institutions. If we focus on the Schumpeter paradigm of innovativeness, which has now become a classic model of setting goals and objectives for social institutions as actors, then innovations in education can be represented as a special social process of creating new forms and models of education, models of teaching, teaching through the practical use of innovations and technologies. The teacher should be ready to constantly search and find new teaching methods that will meet the needs of society and the needs of categories of students. In the guidance documents of the Ministry of Education of the Uzbek Republic after the signing of the Bologna Convention, this approach is designated as a transition from an explanatory model of education based on the translation of knowledge to a competence model. A significant part of the latter is occupied by the process of forming the skills and abilities of graduates of schools and universities to survive in a socially, economically and politically complex structured society. On the one hand, awareness of the future problems that a future graduate will face contributes to the introduction of new subjects, the creation of new teaching methods, the formulation of new, large-scale tasks in education, the final result of which should be the preparation of a person for effective and productive activities in various socially significant situations. In modern state educational standards, this readiness is designated as competencies, about which endless discussions are conducted, since there is no unambiguous definition of the essence of this category. Most often, competence is considered as "actions, understanding of the problem, analysis, search for solutions and activities to solve the problem and achieve a result" [2, p. 19;].

On the other hand, the desire to replace the old paradigm with innovations can also have negative social consequences. According to the researchers, the provisions of the Bologna Convention in Europe are advisory in nature, and in Uzbekistan they are perceived as the truth in the first instance, which does not require critical analysis and reflection [8, p. 112]. Based on the basic concepts of the Bologna model, some researchers believe that the former education is not only outdated, but it is, no less, "aimed mainly at the development of intelligence as the main condition for individual and social development, while other resources of human and human evolution are not involved in it" [7, pp. 354-355].

But the question arises: is it not the development of intelligence, if this concept is understood as "the ability to create", that all modern educational reforms in Uzbekistan are striving for? If this is not the case, then logically it should be recognized that there is something else behind the reforms that is deeply hidden from the consciousness of the layman who wants to get a quality education for himself and his children. The desire to avoid the explanatory paradigm as much as possible, as one of the goals of innovative changes, is already reflected in the quality of education

in the form of a reduction in hours for studying not only "ineffective" humanities, but also fundamental, natural science disciplines that create "excess knowledge"; a decrease in students' motivation for independent work, a drop in the level of education of school graduates and, accordingly, there is a decrease in the requirements for applicants to universities, a drop in constructive thinking, a deterioration in operating with existing knowledge, etc. In 2016, according to the results of inspections in the country's schools, 55% of second grade students could not make a sentence out of the given words. The problems of higher education in recent years have become the subject field of numerous discussions. Particular emphasis is placed on the introduction of new teaching methods, which are designed to compensate for the helplessness of students and teachers in the face of constant reforms in education, which are criticized both by the pedagogical community and by state officials, who are forced to admit that over the years of reforms, Uzbek secondary and higher education has lost its leading positions in many areas: mathematics, physics, engineering and others. Schoolchildren, and then students, can reproduce knowledge, but they cannot explain it. Obviously, the desire of the reformers of the 2000s to bring Uzbek education under universal models (foresight "Education-2030", "Global Universities", "Dublin descriptors", etc.) led to the deprivation of its basic foundations, the destruction of classical foundations, the destruction of traditional attitudes and the replacement of these values with market, more precisely, service services. Vasiliev calls this approach "market fundamentalism", which he characterizes as "the illegal expansion of the market economy and market thinking into non-economic spheres of activity" [10].

But the question arises: what did Tom acquire? He acquired a lot of valuable, in his opinion, items. But he did not learn how to work, painting the fence for him remained an unattractive occupation. And his friends will also get used to working only if someone offers them an exciting activity. An active form of play teaches us to think that all learning should become entertainment, not work. And this is the main danger of using active and interactive teaching methods. They, for all their attractiveness, create an illusion, in the words of J. Dewey, "simplifying social life", reducing it, "where possible, to the simplest forms" [11].

Education and science, Dewey continues, are just tools for organizing life experiences. In this regard, instrumental disciplines are preferred in education to the detriment of essential ones. "Instrumental" disciplines help students learn approaches to solving life problems, while "essential" disciplines encourage "broad thinking" that has no practical application. It was in this vein that Dewey built his education system, which became widespread in the United States and Europe. In the post-revolutionary period of Uzbekistan's history, there were attempts to adopt this system as a career-oriented model of education in the Soviet state. But in the end, there remained a system focused on traditionally broad and deep education, in which there was a place for poetry, history, and art.

Summarizing the above, we can identify three reasons why the innovation model proposed in the past and cultivated in the present is going with great difficulty.

They are simple, but their consequences are very significant. One of them is the need for significant financing of innovations, coordination of financial and material costs, especially in the difficult socio-economic and social political situation in Uzbekistan.

The second reason is the mass training of enthusiastic teachers who are ready to give their time and energy to experiments in education, ready to completely dissolve in these processes.

The third reason is the selection of new teaching methods. A teacher both at school and at a university should concentrate on the interests of his wards and catch "where the wind blows" every meeting, where and how to direct the work of students, especially in conditions of strict requirements of curricula to increase attention to individual work with students.

But focusing on individual work only on this subject reduces attention to other tasks of curricula and curricula, overshadows all other points of the curriculum, which include versatile skills and knowledge. And, besides, there are no such institutions yet where they could train teachers with such a huge range of skills that educational standards require.

Thus, the analysis of only a part of the general problems of innovative transformations leads us to the conclusion that there is a need for a balanced approach to the ongoing changes in the Uzbek education system. The same conclusion applies to the technologies used, many of which, for all their advantages, cannot replace a teacher in a lecture and seminar audience.

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